

SPATIUM, TOOLS FOR SOUND SPATIALIZATION

Rui Penha

Universidade de Aveiro / INET-MD
rui@ruipenha.pt

João Pedro Oliveira

Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais
jppo@ua.pt

ABSTRACT

In this paper we present *spatium*, a set of free, open source and modular software tools for sound spatialization, describing the creative and technical aspects considered during its development. The system is comprised of spatialization renderers, spatialization interfaces, DAW plugins and Max objects that communicate via OSC (Open Sound Control). They aim to: facilitate the exploration of different approaches to sound spatialization, ease the integration of sound spatialization into diverse compositional workflows, smooth the transition from the studio to different performance environments and be easily expandable to cater for growing needs.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sound is always in space, in the sense that "there is no non-spatial hearing" [1], and the experimental placement of sounds in space as a musical parameter is something that dates back to at least the 16th century. Nevertheless, the intentional control of sound spatialization is undoubtedly amongst the most important conquests of electroacoustic music. It is thus without surprise that a survey of recent research (or even just a quick search online) reveals the existence of many tools for sound spatialization, either commercial or freely available, and several composers developing their own custom solutions for specific pieces. We aim to contribute to this field with the recent release of *spatium*, a set of free, open source and modular software tools for sound spatialization. It is comprised of: three spatialization renderers, ten spatialization interfaces, one Audio Unit plugin, two Max for Live devices and four Max objects. Both the software and its source are available for download at <http://spatium.ruipenha.pt>, where one can also find online documentation for all the elements, a short video tutorial and a musical example.

1.1 Why (yet) another spatialization tool?

Most composers still use the built-in panning devices of either their DAWs (Digital Audio Workstations) or hardware mixing consoles as their primary spatialization tools, albeit being conscious of their limitations [2]. As it is also a common practice amongst composers working with sound spatialization, we set out to build *spatium* as a custom-made

system, with specific goals that existing tools did not fully address:

- simple integration with DAWs, including ones that are limited to stereo busses (e.g., Ableton Live), allowing the recording of spatial information as plugin automation;
- easy adjustment to different studio and performance environments, maximizing portability and taking advantage of increased spatial resolution at particular venues;
- ability to choose the most suitable interface paradigm for each musical intention, including gestural control of spatialization, kinematic spatialization and introducing some novel approaches to dynamic spatialization;
- ability to facilitate the realtime use of sound spatialization through intuitive interfaces, minimizing the need to fully grasp the technical details of a given spatialization technique in advance.

spatium is still a work in progress that can greatly benefit from the contribution of the community. We have therefore decided to share it as both free and open source software.

1.2 Why modular?

A stratified approach has been identified as fruitful solution to integrate sound spatialization into different compositional needs and to allow different combinations of rendering algorithms and controlling interfaces [3]. This modular approach also benefits from the current trend of multi-core processors, by enabling the distribution of processing between multiple cores, processors or even machines. Being open source software, the modular architecture also caters for the users who may want to integrate the proposed interfaces with their own spatialization renderers or the other way around: the Processing community, e.g., has built many sketches that could easily be repurposed as spatialization interfaces for *spatium*¹.

2. ARCHITECTURE

As can be seen on Fig. 1, a simple *spatium* system is composed of three main elements:

- the spatialization renderer - which receives monophonic audio channels, the spatial information for

Copyright: ©2013 Rui Penha et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

¹ Many examples can be found at <http://www.openprocessing.org>.

- each channel and renders the result for a chosen loudspeaker layout;
- the spatialization interface - which generates spatial information to send, either via OSC to the spatialization renderer or via Midi to be stored as plugin automation at a specific DAW track;
- the Audio Unit plugin or the Max for Live device - which stores spatial information as automation and sends it, via OSC and synchronized with the audio, to the spatialization renderer.

Figure 1. The modular architecture of *spatium*.

2.1 Coordinate System

spatium exclusively uses spherical coordinates: azimuth 0° is in front and increases clockwise; elevation 0° is at the horizontal plane at ear level and increases towards the top; radius goes from 0.0 at the origin to 1.0 at the surface of the soundfield. This is known as the navigational coordinate system and was chosen because of its familiarity, namely due to its previous use in other spatialization tools [4].

2.2 Communication protocol

Communication protocols to send spatialization data over OSC have been proposed, most notably SpatDIF [5]. We chose, however, to develop our own protocol, as in order to be compliant with SpatDIF, an audio renderer must understand and interpret all its core statements, which include descriptors that *spatium* does not use (e.g., orientation) and default position to Cartesian coordinates, as opposed to *spatium*'s exclusive use of spherical coordinates. SpatDIF was developed mainly to control several spatialization renderers from one common interface, whilst *spatium*'s main goal was to enable the control of a chosen spatialization renderer using several interfaces at once. As the audio renderers and the interfaces of *spatium* were developed in parallel within an integrated approach, their protocol requirements are much simpler than the ones needed to provide universal control over different approaches.

One can communicate with the spatialization renderers using four types of messages, send via UDP to port 11475:

- `/spatium/#/aer f1 f2 f3`

- `/spatium/#/azimuth f1`
- `/spatium/#/elevation f2`
- `/spatium/#/radius f3`

with # being the channel, from 1 to 16^2 , and $f1 f2 f3$ being, respectively, its azimuth, elevation and radius.

3. SPATIALIZATION TECHNIQUES

spatium uses two spatialization techniques, one based on Ambisonics with distance encoding - used in *spatium-ambi*, along with its related renderers and of their underlying Max objects - and another one based on amplitude panning between stereo pairs - used in *spatium-panning* and its homonymous max object. Both techniques include some novel strategies for the placement of sounds inside of the soundfield that are specific to *spatium*.

3.1 Ambisonics with distance encoding

Ambisonics has recently regained much interest, in part for its ability to encode spatial audio independently of the reproduction setup. High Order Ambisonics can provide greater spatial resolution while maintaining scalability, backwards compatibility, superior immersiveness and reproduction of moving sound sources. The encoding format used in *spatium* is fixed as a mixed-order Ambisonics soundfield, using a 3rd order horizontal, 1st order vertical approach. The choice of having superior resolution on the horizontal plane was made due to the ubiquity of horizontal-only loudspeaker systems and also because our perception of localization has much better resolution on the horizontal plane than on the median plane [1]. By using mixed-order Ambisonics encoding, we are able to minimize the number of audio channels needed to encode the soundfield, whilst retaining periphonic capabilities. We chose, however, to use a 12-channel 3H1V instead of traditional 8-channel 3H1P, as originally proposed by Jérôme Daniel [6], in order to retain horizontal resolution even when going up in the soundfield.

To this 12-channel 3H1V mixed-order Ambisonics soundfield, an additional channel is added for distance encoding, as we have proposed before [7]. This approach is related to W-panning [8] and B Format Inside Panner [9], as they all encode sounds inside the speaker array by increasing the omnidirectional component while decreasing the directional components of the Ambisonics soundfield. Our proposal is distinguished by isolating the sounds at the center of the space in a specific channel, through the use of an additional angular coordinate. This system allows for the postponing of the application of cues for the perception of distance to the decoding stage, where they can be adapted to the characteristics of a specific space and sound system.

3.2 Amplitude panning between stereo pairs

This technique is used in *spatium* as an alternative to the main Ambisonics renderers and objects, using amplitude

² Using standard OSC notation, this number can be replaced by an asterisk * to control all channels simultaneously.

panning with the least possible number of speakers, ideally only a stereo pair, to spatialize a sound inside a concentric loudspeaker layout with an arbitrary number and placement of loudspeakers. When placing a sound close to the circumference defined by the loudspeakers, it will pan the sound between the two closest speakers, as it happens with 2D VBAP [10], using either sine or square root panning laws. When placing the sound inside the circle, it will use the azimuth to determine a stereo pair, the opposite azimuth (azimuth - 180°) to determine a second stereo pair and the radius to amplitude pan between them. Whilst these phantom images across the soundfield do not work as traditional stereo phantom images, due to the interference of the listener's head, this approach enables some spatialization effects such as the rotation around the vertical axis of a sound placed in the middle of the soundfield, by keeping its radius 0.0 whilst changing its azimuth. Three concrete scenarios can be seen on Fig. 2: to pan sound a, the algorithm will do an amplitude panning between speakers 1 and 2; to pan sound b, the algorithm will do an amplitude panning between speakers 1 and 5; to pan sound c, the algorithm will do an amplitude panning between speakers 3 and 4, an amplitude panning between speakers 7 and 8 and finally an amplitude panning between these two pairs.

Figure 2. Three scenarios of amplitude panning between stereo pairs.

3.3 Max objects

These techniques were implemented as Max objects, including three Ambisonics-based objects - *spatium-encode*, *spatium-decode* and *spatium-rotate* - and one Amplitude panning-based object - *spatium-panning*, along with some auxiliary patches. They were used to develop *spatium*'s renderers and are documented on the included help files. As *spatium-panning* is a new technique, it required the development of a new object, but many objects have already been developed for Ambisonics-based spatialization in Max/MSP [11–14]. Any one of these existing libraries provides a very flexible and rich approach to Ambisonics

spatialization and it would have been possible to implement *spatium-ambi* using them. We nevertheless felt the need to develop our own Ambisonics-based objects, not only to expand the encoding and decoding capabilities with our proposal for distance encoding, but also to incorporate some of the characteristics of the popular VBAP object [15] that we found particularly interesting. Most Ambisonics-based libraries of objects for Max require the user to have some previous knowledge about the idiosyncrasies of Ambisonics (e.g., spherical harmonic orders, order weighting). This knowledge is of course helpful to get good results, as it is true with any technique, but their complexity contrasts with VBAP's simplicity. *spatium*'s objects, as the VBAP object, do not process audio, relying instead on the standard matrix~ MSP object to render the audio. This makes the objects' code easier to maintain and their output simpler to hack for specific needs. Both the Ambisonics and Amplitude panning implementations of the *spatium* objects were designed to be easily interchangeable with the VBAP in existing Max/MSP patches.

4. SPATIALIZATION RENDERERS

spatium has four spatialization renderers, three based on Ambisonics with distance encoding - *spatium-ambi*, *spatium-player* and *spatium-diffusion* - and another one based on amplitude panning between stereo pairs - *spatium-panning*.

4.1 spatium-ambi

spatium-ambi receives mono audio channels and encodes them into an Ambisonics soundfield with distance encoding. The spatial information to encode each channel is received via OSC. The resulting soundfield can be decoded to several loudspeaker layouts, enabling the composition of spatial music with (almost) any loudspeaker setup and the fine-tuning of the piece to any given performance setup. As it was conceived to be used alongside other applications, the main goal when designing its GUI was to make it as compact as possible. As can be seen on Fig. 3, the top portion shows the renderer's 16 monophonic audio inputs, each with its own amplitude meter and three floating-point number displays showing its azimuth, elevation and radius. The bottom portion shows the controls over specific points of the audio engine, with the input to output path laid out from left to right.

Figure 3. The GUI of the *spatium-ambi* renderer.

4.1.1 Granular spatialization

Some approaches have been proposed for the spatialization of granular audio, namely by using swarm-based algorithms to define the grains' positions in space [16, 17].

The granular settings' panel controls several parameters of a granular engine based on Nathan Wolek's granular toolkit [18]. This engine feeds a sound file into four granular generators whose output iterates through four outputs each, giving a total of 16 grain streams that can be individually assigned to any of the 16 channels available at the encoding stage.

4.1.2 Spectral spatialization

Some approaches have been proposed for spectral spatialization [16, 19], a technique that opens several possibilities to mingle timbre and space into cohesive gestures. When activated, the spectral engine divides the live audio input into 28 frequency bands that can be individually silenced or assigned to any of the 16 channels available at the decoding stage.

4.1.3 Decoding loudspeaker layouts

Concentric and equally spaced loudspeaker setups are the ideal means for the reproduction of a decoded soundfield. Regular polygons and Platonic solids are the most obvious solutions for equally spaced layouts and they constitute the major part of the presets of *spatium-ambi* (and of its underlying *spatium-decode* Max object). For the 3D (periphonic) layouts, we used four of the Platonic solids: hexahedron, octahedron, dodecahedron and icosahedron. For the 2D (horizontal) layouts, we used six of the regular polygons, based on the ones we most frequently found at performance venues: square, pentagon, hexagon, octagon, dodecagon and hexadecagon. The stereo output uses the traditional Ambisonic 2-channel UHJ format [20], with minor modification to include the distance decoding. We have found this stereo decoding very pleasing and capable of giving a reliable rendering of an horizontal-only environment, for when the composer is forced to work with solely the ubiquitous stereo monitoring. We have also included a decoder for the standard ITU 5.1 layout and a horizontal-only binaural option, using recent HRTF Measurements of a KEMAR manikin [21]. This binaural implementation is based on the decoding of the soundfield into a regular 24-gon loudspeaker, convoluted with stereo HRTF for each of these positions. By replacing the *hrtf#.aif* files included with the source code (with # being an integer from 1 to 24 representing the loudspeakers from azimuth 0° onwards with a 15° increment), one can easily use customized HRTF Measurements.

4.1.4 Decoder settings

The control of the order weights is something that is very important to control the reproduction characteristics, namely the spatial resolution or the size of the sweet spot. However, it can be a difficult concept to grasp for composers with little knowledge about the Ambisonics' underlying math. In *spatium-ambi*, each loudspeaker layout choice automatically adjusts which Ambisonic orders to use and with what weights, defaulting to a *max-rE* decoder [22]. In the decoder settings panel, one can adjust the rotation of the soundfield and the order weights. In order to simulate distance cues such as loudness, atmospheric absorption or

near-field effect [23] at the decoding stage, one can also adjust the level of the center portion of the soundfield and its equalization.

4.1.5 Reverb settings

The natural reverberation is usually one of the most difficult characteristics to predict and control at performance venues. We have thus decided to include a reverb at the decoding stage, so its characteristics can be adjusted at the time of performance. It is a convolution reverb, using the B-format (i.e., 1st order Ambisonics) impulse responses available at the Open AIR Library [24], along with HISSTools' *multiconvolve~* object [25] for realtime convolution. The fact that the impulse responses have less spatial resolution than the soundfield being decoded is not a big problem for diffuse reverberation purposes, but it does imply that, in order not to lose spatial resolution, the dry signal must always be present. After choosing the impulse response, one can manipulate its equalization, the reverb gain and, most importantly as a distance cue, the amount of reverb being applied to the center channel. Albeit using non-optimized impulse responses, this reverb implementation gives a satisfactory definition of acoustical spaces that appear to be bigger than the performance venue.

4.1.6 *spatium-player* and *spatium-diffusion*

These two renderers are based on *spatium-ambi*, both have the same output options and can share the same preset files, presenting a smaller GUI with a waveform display on top. *spatium-player* is a player for pre-encoded soundfields and *spatium-diffusion* can be used to perform live diffusion of pre-existing stereo works.

4.2 *spatium-panning*

Unlike the realtime, spatialization mixing-board concept of *spatium-ambi*, *spatium-panning* was designed for the spatialization of individual sound files before their sequencing and mixing in a DAW. This renderer thus takes an audio file and spatializes it to any 2D, concentric loudspeaker setup (up to 24 channels) using amplitude panning between stereo pairs. The loudspeaker configuration does not have to be regular and the same sound and path can be rendered to different loudspeaker configurations by just enabling or disabling specific loudspeaker locations. The spatialization path can be constructed and edited as a polygonal chain synchronized with the original audio file, using the GUI visible on Fig. 4. *spatium-panning* can also receive OSC from *spatium's* interfaces to be recorded as a spatialization path for further editing. The end result can then be rendered as a set of mono audio files, one for each loudspeaker feed.

5. SPATIALIZATION INTERFACES

Some existing stratified tools for sound spatialization focus on the possibility of controlling "different spatial rendering algorithms from one common interface" [3]. We believe that the most interesting capability of this modular approach, from a composer's perspective, is actually the

Figure 4. The GUI of the *spatium-ambi* renderer.

other way around. Each interface has its own interaction vocabulary and enforces a specific approach, even if solely by making the composer’s vision cumbersome to implement. We have addressed this before, both in terms of designing GUIs specifically to explore this binding between interface and composition technique [26] and in terms of the dangers of confining to the idiosyncrasies of one interface when controlling a musical parameter [27].

We have therefore developed several interfaces (ten at the moment of this writing) that enable both traditional and novel approaches to sound spatialization and that are employable with all the spatialization renderers. We divide these into three categories: dynamic spatialization, kinematic spatialization and gestural spatialization. These interfaces send the spatial information either by OSC messages or by Midi controller values, with most of their parameters being also controllable via OSC. As Midi controller values are generic by nature and the OSC ip, port and addresses are customisable, these interfaces can also be used to generate data for purposes other than spatialization.

5.1 Dynamic spatialization

Dynamic spatialization is the spatialization of sound whose control is focused on the causes of movement, as opposed to the traditional focus on the geometry of motion, characteristic of kinematic spatialization. Inspired by several approaches with swarm spatialization [16, 17] and the Sound Swing series by Bernhard Leitner [28], we developed interfaces where the manipulation of forces like gravity or friction supersedes the traditional control over key frame positions and velocities.

spatium-pendulum and *spatium-flocking* are 3D spatialization interfaces that share some GUI characteristics, visible on Fig. 5. The control within a 3D space using a 2D computer environment is made possible by interacting with one of three 2D projections. These are, from bottom left and on clockwise order, the projection on the horizontal plane, the projection on the frontal plane and the projection on the median plane. The menu on the bottom right corner can be hidden to reveal a one-point perspective 3D view over the scene. The *spatium-pendulum* interface simulates

Figure 5. The GUI of the *spatium-pendulum* interface.

Figure 6. The GUI of the *spatium-gravityBalls2D* interface. The control over the azimuth of the gravitational force can be seen underneath the main circle.

a 3D pendulum, with controllable pivot position, gravity and damping. The *spatium-flocking* interface uses a flocking algorithm to move up to 16 birds in a 3D space, generating movements that work particularly well with granular synthesis, as suggested by previous research [16, 17].

spatium-pendulum2D, *spatium-gravityBalls2D* and *spatium-springs2D* are three interfaces for dynamic spatialization that work solely in the horizontal plane and share a similar GUI to the one visible on Fig. 6. The *spatium-pendulum2D* interface is simply a 2D version of the same algorithm used for the *spatium-pendulum* interface. The *spatium-gravityBalls2D* interface simulates up to 16 balls that are enclosed within the 2D soundfield. Each of these balls has a different radius and is attracted by a gravitational force whose azimuth is controllable, as seen on Fig. 6. The balls bounce on the walls, when they collide with each other and can be launched against the other balls using a slingshot. The *spatium-springs2D* interface simulates up to 6 springs that connect as many anchors to the spatialization particle, which can be launched by dragging and releasing the mouse.

Figure 7. The GUI of the *spatium-polygonalChain2D* interface.

Figure 8. The GUI of the *spatium-rotation* interface.

5.2 Kinematic spatialization

Kinematic spatialization is the spatialization of sound whose control is focused on the geometry of motion (e.g., position, velocity, acceleration), without considering external causes for this movement. They are thus closer to some more traditional interfaces for spatialization. The *spatium-polygonalChain2D* interface, visible on Fig. 7, enables the creation of a spatialization path as a polygonal chain, that can be saved and retrieved for further editing. After creating the polygonal chain, the user can perform the movement by moving a horizontal fader with the mouse or by controlling its position along the timeline via OSC. With the *spatium-rotation* interface, visible on Fig. 8, one controls the angular acceleration on a horizontal plane, with controllable elevation and radius. The movement accelerates clockwise or counter clockwise, moving with either variable or uniform acceleration, when the fader is respectively moving or left in a fixed position, or with constant angular velocity, when the fader is reset to 0.

5.3 Gestural spatialization

Gestural spatialization refers to both the kind of interface and to the relation established between the spatialization and the musical gestures. The gestural spatialization interfaces focus on direct, real-time control over the spatialization particle. The *spatium-linearRotation* interface has a similar GUI to that of the *spatium-rotation* interface, visible on Fig. 8, with the topmost fader now directly controlling the azimuth, with two complete revolutions available. The main purpose is to facilitate the control over the rotation of the spatialization particle using the mouse, which we found to be easier to accomplish using a linear fader instead of a circular controller. With *spatium-trackpad*, one can use the laptop's trackpad as an absolute positioning

touch controller. It controls solely one spatialization particle, as we found the trackpad too small for multi-particle control. The *spatium-controlOSC* interface has two modes that enable the use of Control [29], a free, open source and customizable touch controller that runs on both iOS and Android and outputs OSC via Wi-Fi. The first mode, called *multitouch*, is optimized for a tablet and enables the direct, multi-touch control over up to 16 channels in a 2D space. The second mode, called *gyroscope*, enables the control of the spatialization particle's position in a 3D space by pointing to the desired physical location with, e.g., an iPhone or Android phone.

6. PLUGINS

Both the Audio Unit plugin and the Max for Live devices developed for *spatium* are not actual audio effects and pass the audio untouched to the output. They simply send their parameters via OSC messages, thus enabling the recording and synchronization of spatial information as automation on any compatible DAW.

The *spatium-track* plugin can be placed in an audio track effects chain to send its three parameters - *azimuth*, *elevation* and *radius* - via OSC. Up to 16 instances of this plugin, which uses the generic Audio Unit GUI, can be used simultaneously, but only one can use a given channel at a given time to avoid conflicting information. By setting a spatialization interface to output Midi and configuring the DAW's automation control accordingly, one can record the spatial information generated by *spatium's* interfaces on the same track as the audio being spatialized, enabling its reproduction and further editing.

The *spatium-live* device receives, displays, stores and/or controls spatialization information to be sent via OSC. It can be used instead of *spatium-track* when in Ableton Live, adding the possibility of being controlled directly via OSC.

The *OSCsend* is not a part of *spatium*, instead being a generic device that can record up to three automatable parameters to be sent via OSC to any ip address and port. It can be used to control *spatium's* interfaces by setting the appropriate addresses as parameters.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We hope that *spatium* can successfully facilitate the integration of spatialization in other composers' workflows, at the same time catalysing the emergence of new and creative approaches to sound spatialization. We have been using it for almost a year and it has proven a trustworthy set of tools, capable of promoting some unorthodox approaches to sound spatialization. After its initial release, on October 2012, the feedback from the community has been very encouraging, leading to some of the developments that we have included in this paper, such as the *spatium-panning*, *spatium-player* and *spatium-diffusion* renderers, the control of the interfaces' parameters via OSC or the Max for Live devices. Although we do not have concrete data on the usage of *spatium*, in the first month after the release of the latest version at the time of this writing,

in late March 2013, the website received circa 500 unique visitors.

We plan to release new interfaces, to upgrade the still very basic granular and spectral spatialization effects and to add some new decoding layouts in the near future. Amongst these, we plan to include 3D binaural rendering and potentiate its utility as both a mobile composition aid and as a distribution format. We also plan to implement the capability of imposing audio effects into specific points of the soundfield, as we have proposed before [7]. The first practical uses of *spatium* also revealed the need for a simple mixer that enables the amplitude manipulation and summing of several soundfields placed on a timeline. The *spatium-panning* object's algorithm will also be expanded with a 3D version.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia for supporting our work.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] J. Blauert, *Spatial Hearing*. The MIT Press, 1997.
- [2] N. Peters, G. Marentakis, and S. McAdams, "Current technologies and compositional practices for spatialization: a qualitative and quantitative analysis," *Computer Music J.*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 10–27, 2011.
- [3] N. Peters, T. Lossius, J. Schacher, P. Baltazar, C. Bascou, and T. Place, "A stratified approach for sound spatialization," in *Proc. SMC*, Porto, 2009.
- [4] V. Schacher, "Seven years of ICST ambisonics tools for Max/MSP - a brief report," in *Proc. Ambisonics Symposium*, Paris, 2010.
- [5] N. Peters, T. Lossius, and J. Schacher, "SpatDIF: Principles, specification, and examples," in *Proc. SMC*, Copenhagen, 2012.
- [6] C. Travis, "A new mixed-order scheme for ambisonic signals," in *Proc. Ambisonics Symposium*, Graz, 2009.
- [7] R. Penha, "Distance encoding in ambisonics using three angular coordinates," in *Proc. SMC*, Berlin, 2008.
- [8] D. Menzies, "W-Panning and O-Format, tools for object spatialization," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Auditory Display*, Kyoto, 2002.
- [9] M. Morrell and J. Reiss, "A comparative approach to sound localisation within a 3D sound field," in *Proc. 126th AES Convention*, Munich, 2009.
- [10] V. Pulkki, "Virtual sound source positioning using vector base amplitude panning," *J. AES*, vol. 45, no. 6, pp. 456–466, 1997.
- [11] J. Schacher and P. Kocher, "Ambisonics spatialization tools for Max/MSP," in *Proc. ICMC*, New Orleans, 2006.
- [12] G. Wakefield, "Third-order ambisonic extensions for Max/MSP with musical applications," in *Proc. ICMC*, New Orleans, 2006.
- [13] G. Wakefield and W. Smith, "Cosm: a toolkit for composing immersive audio-visual worlds of agency and autonomy," in *Proc. ICMC*, Huddersfield, 2011.
- [14] J. Colafrancesco, "L'ambisonie d'ordre supérieur et son appropriation par les musiciens, présentation de la bibliothèque Hoa.lib," in *Journées d'Informatique Musicale*, Mons, 2012.
- [15] V. Pulkki, "Generic panning tools for Max/MSP," in *Proc. ICMC*, Berlin, 2000.
- [16] D. Kim-Boyle, "Spectral and granular spatialization with boids," in *Proc. ICMC*, New Orleans, 2006.
- [17] S. Wilson, "Spatial swarm granulation," in *Proc. ICMC*, Belfast, 2008.
- [18] N. Wolek, "A granular toolkit for Cycling'74's Max/MSP," in *Proc. SEAMUS Nat. Conf.*, Iowa City, 2002.
- [19] R. Torchia and C. Lippe, "Techniques for multi-channel real-time spatial distribution using frequency-domain processing," in *Proc. Int. Conf. NIME*, Hamamatsu, 2004.
- [20] Wikipedia. Ambisonic UHJ format. Accessed on February 2013. [Online]. Available: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ambisonic_UHJ_format
- [21] H. Wierstorf, M. Geier, A. Raake, and S. Spors, "A free database of head-related impulse response measurements in the horizontal plane with multiple distances," in *Proc. 130th AES Convention*, London, 2011.
- [22] F. Hollerweger, "Periphonic sound spatialization in multi-user virtual environments," Master's thesis, IEM/CREATE, 2006.
- [23] J. Daniel, "Spatial sound encoding including near field effect: Introducing distance coding filters and a viable, new ambisonic format," in *Proc. AES 23rd Int. Conf.*, Copenhagen, 2003.
- [24] T. U. of York. OpenAIR library. Accessed on February 2013. [Online]. Available: <http://www.openairlib.net>
- [25] A. Harker and P. Tremblay, "The HISSTools impulse response toolbox: Convolution for the masses," in *Proc. ICMC*, Ljubljana, 2012.
- [26] R. Penha, "Towards a free, open source and cross-platform software suite for approaching music and sound design," in *Research, Reflections and Innovations in Integrating ICT in Education*, A. Méndez-Villas, A. S. Martín, and J. M. González, Eds. Badajoz: Formatex, 2009, pp. 1204–1208.
- [27] J. Oliveira, "Tecnologia, fetichismo e crise de identidade," 2012, unpublished manuscript.

- [28] B. Leitner, *Sound:Space*. Cantz Verlag, 1998.
- [29] C. Roberts. Control. Accessed on February 2013. [Online]. Available: <http://charlie-roberts.com/Control/>